

High-frequency electric current welding with suprachoroidal approach to treat retinal detachment: timing of morphological changes and strength of chorioretinal adhesion.

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Introduction

Chorioretinal adhesions (CRA) are essential in retinal detachment surgery. A high-frequency electric current welding (HFECW) has been recently shown to be a suitable technique for the colligation of biological tissues [1,2]. Application of HFECW in retinal detachment surgery aims to develop a method for instant and effective tissue adhesion with minimal damage to the retina, which doesn't require pigment epithelium (RPE) to form adhesions (relevant for high myopia and repeated operations) and omits the use of long-term tamponade.

To evaluate the morphological changes (MC) and CRA strength (CRAS), a HFECW was applied with suprachoroidal and transvitreal approach on an experimental animal model to cause CRA.

Material and Methods

The study was carried out according to the guidelines for the care and use of experimental animals and according to the Association for Research in Vision and Ophthalmology (ARVO) for the use of animals in ophthalmic and visual research. The experiments were conducted on 54 adult chinchilla rabbits in the operating room (Fig.1A) under intravenous general anesthesia. A modified EK-300M1 generator (Kyiv, Ukraine) was used for HFECW (Fig.1B). Parameters used: frequency 66 kHz, voltage 10-12 volts (V), 12-14 V, 14-16 V with a current of 0.1 amperes (A). A gold hemispheric 25-gauge tip served as the working surface of the instrument (Fig.1C,D). After euthanasia, a histological analysis of the tissues affected by HFECW using the suprachoroidal and transvitreal approach with different modes was performed (Fig.1E,F).

To determine the strength of the chorioretinal adhesion, an original device based on electronic scales was developed and assembled (Fig.1G). The sclera was fixed on the electronic scales. 0.5 mm from the welding site, the retina was tied with a 10-0 thread to the electronic scales by the method of elongation to the power of the engine. The task of this device was to pull a 10-0 thread attached to the retina at the same steady speed. The strength of adhesion was recorded on an electric scale in milligrams (mg).

Results

In all treated eyes, the monopolar HFECW induced an increased tissue adhesion in the area of electrode application, which strengthened with time. The retina responded by apparent destruction of rods, cones, loss of bipolar, amacrine, horizontal and ganglion cells, development of cysts and migration of RPEs (Fig.2,3). The choroid showed damage and migration of melanocytes. By day 30, tissue thinning with partial cell regeneration and connective tissue degeneration was apparent (Fig.4A,B). Amplification of the voltage from 10 to 16 V caused a shift from active exudation without significant tissue damage to acute retinal necrosis, respectively (Fig.2,3). The nearby retinal layers and vitreous remained intact.

After the application of local suprachoroidal HFECW with a frequency of 66 kHz using three voltage modes, the strength of the chorioretinal adhesion was significantly greater compared to the indicators of chorioretinal adhesion on the intact retina (control group)(Fig 5A).

In the early periods after the exposure (up to 2 weeks), the strength of the chorioretinal connection was the highest when exposed to a voltage of 10-12 V, compared to higher voltage parameters (12-14 V, 14-16 V). But already a month after suprachoroidal HFECW, there was no significant difference between the groups (Fig.5B).

Figures

Figure 1. Experimental settings for the study of HFECW-induced CRA using transvitreal and suprachoroidal approach A, B, C, D, E, F (see details in the text). G - schematic drawing of the device-controlled biomechanical force elongation tester.

Figure 2. Morphology of the CRA in the rabbit's eye 3 days after suprachoroidal exposure to HFECW with 10-12 V (A), 12-14 V (B) and 14-16 V (C,D). A, B: 1 - swelling of the interstitium in the sclera; 2 - coagulation of large vessels in the choroid; 3 - swelling of the interstitium and destruction of rods and cones of the photoreceptor layer; 4 - focal swelling of the interstitium in the outer nuclear layer; 5 - focal edema of the interstitium in the inner nuclear layer; 6 - exfoliation of the internal boundary membrane. C,D: 1 - coagulation of large vessels in the choroid; 2 - swelling of the interstitium in the choroid; 3 - swelling of the interstitium of the photoreceptor layer of the retina; 4 - focal swelling of the interstitium in the outer nuclear layer; 5 - external plexiform layer; 6 - focal swelling of the inner nuclear layer; 7 - ganglion cell layer; 8 - nerve fibers layer; 9 - detachment of the vitreous body.

Figure 3. Morphology of the chorio-retinal adhesion in the rabbit's eye 7 days (A,B,C) and 30 days (D,E,F) after suprachoroidal exposure to HFECW.

Figure 4. Morphology of the CRA in the rabbits' eye 30 days after the surgery using transvitreal (A) and suprachoroidal (B) approach.

Figure 5. A - The strength of the CRA after the application of local suprachoroidal HFECW. B - Changes of the strength of the CRA over the 1 month period.

Conclusions

Application of HFECW with suprachoroidal approach induces a chorio-retinal adhesion within 1 hour after the treatment, and it strengthens within first weeks.

- The extent of atrophic changes strongly depends on the voltage and is less pronounced when using a voltage of 10-12 V.
- The transvitreal approach demonstrates pronounced retinal changes compared to the suprachoroidal one, where the retina adjacent to the focus of electric welding remained histologically less damaged.
- The less energy we apply the better adhesion we achieve in the early period, However, one month later after the exposure, the adhesion force is equalized in different voltage ranges, and there is no statistically significant difference between the groups.

Implementation of HFECW as an alternative method to treat retinal detachment could reduce the need for long-term endotamponade and the associated risks of complications.

References

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